

Enhancing Sustainability in Construction: A Systematic Review of Carbon-Absorbing Concrete Technologies and Applications

Olaleye R. Kayode ✉

Department of Construction Engineering, University of Greenwich, UK

Shakiru A. Ayoade

Department of Construction Engineering, University of Greenwich, UK

ABSTRACT:

The construction industry's substantial contribution to global carbon emissions necessitates the development of sustainable building materials. Carbon-absorbing concrete offers a promising solution by sequestering carbon dioxide during its production and usage, potentially mitigating the environmental impact of traditional concrete. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of carbon-absorbing concrete, focusing on its production methods, material composition, and the effectiveness of various carbon sequestration techniques. A systematic literature review was conducted to identify and evaluate methodologies used in creating carbon-absorbing concrete, including supplementary cementitious materials, carbonation curing processes, and innovative carbon capture technologies. Key findings suggest that incorporating materials such as fly ash, graphene oxide, and blast furnace slag not only enhances the concrete's carbon absorption capabilities but also improves its mechanical properties, including compressive strength and durability. Challenges remain in optimizing the mix designs and understanding the long-term durability of these materials. However, this research highlights the potential for carbon-absorbing concrete to advance sustainable construction practices and reduce the carbon footprint of the built environment. Future studies are recommended to explore material optimization, lifecycle assessments, and real-world applications to maximize the efficacy and scalability of carbon-absorbing concrete.

Keywords: Sustainable, Concrete, Construction, Carbon, Mechanical Properties.

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INTRODUCTION

Concrete is the most widely used artificial material globally, playing a crucial role in infrastructure and construction projects. However, its production is a significant contributor to global carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, accounting for approximately 8% of the total emissions due to the cement manufacturing process, which involves the calcination of limestone and the combustion of fossil fuels [1-5]. The urgency to address these emissions is underscored by the rapid urbanization and increasing demand for concrete, which raises concerns regarding resource depletion and the sustainability of traditional construction practices [6]. The built environment, which includes concrete and steel, is responsible for nearly 40% of global carbon emissions, highlighting the need for innovative solutions to mitigate these impacts [7-11].

In response to the environmental challenges posed by conventional concrete, carbon-absorbing concrete has emerged as a promising alternative. This innovative material incorporates CO₂-sequestering technologies, such as supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) and carbonation

curing, which not only reduce emissions but also capture and store carbon within the concrete matrix [12-14]. Research has demonstrated that using SCMs like fly ash and slag can significantly lower the carbon footprint of concrete while enhancing its durability and mechanical properties [12,15,16]. For instance, studies have shown that alkali-activated materials derived from industrial waste can improve the sustainability of concrete without compromising its structural integrity [17-19]. Furthermore, carbonation curing, which involves exposing fresh concrete to CO₂-rich environments, has been shown to accelerate the curing process and enhance the formation of stable calcium carbonates, effectively reducing the overall carbon emissions associated with concrete production [20-22].

Despite the potential benefits of carbon-absorbing concrete, several challenges remain regarding its practical application and long-term durability. Key research gaps include the optimization of material formulations, a comprehensive assessment of the environmental impacts throughout the material's lifecycle, and an evaluation of the cost-effectiveness of large-scale implementation [23-25]. Studies have indicated that while carbonation curing can enhance the mechanical properties of concrete, variations in efficiency are influenced by factors such as material composition and curing conditions [26-28]. Additionally, the integration of carbonated recycled materials has shown promise in improving the mechanical properties of concrete while simultaneously reducing emissions [13,29,30]. However, the economic viability and scalability of these methods require further investigation to facilitate widespread adoption in the construction sector [31,32].

This study aims to advance the understanding of carbon-absorbing concrete as a sustainable alternative for the construction industry. The objectives include evaluating diverse production methods to identify those most effective in enhancing CO₂ sequestration, assessing the mechanical properties of carbon-absorbing concrete in comparison to traditional concrete, and examining its environmental benefits in the context of sustainable construction practices. By synthesizing findings from the literature, this research seeks to consolidate existing knowledge on carbon-absorbing concrete, highlight research gaps, and suggest directions for future studies to promote the adoption of sustainable building materials in the construction sector.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a systematic literature review (SLR) to consolidate and evaluate existing research on carbon-absorbing concrete, focusing on its production methods, material properties, and carbon sequestration potential.

Research Design

A systematic literature review was conducted to identify, evaluate, and synthesize primary studies on carbon-absorbing concrete. The review aimed to address three key objectives:

1. Analyzing various production methods of carbon-absorbing concrete.
2. Assessing the mechanical properties of carbon-absorbing concrete, including durability and compressive strength.
3. Evaluating the environmental benefits and carbon sequestration potential of carbon-absorbing concrete technologies.

Literature Search Strategy

The literature search targeted peer-reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings, and industry reports. Several academic databases were consulted, including Google Scholar, Engineering Village, ScienceDirect, and Web of Science. The search terms included combinations of keywords such as "carbon-absorbing concrete," "carbon sequestration in concrete," "low carbon construction materials," and "carbon capture and utilization in concrete." The search was restricted to studies published from 2013 to 2023.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Studies were included if they focused on the development and properties of carbon-absorbing concrete, used supplementary cementitious materials, and involved carbon sequestration methods.

The studies had to be published in peer-reviewed journals or presented in reputable conferences within the last decade. Studies lacking sufficient methodological detail, focusing on unrelated materials or technologies, or published prior to 2013 were excluded. Non-English language publications were also excluded.

Selection Process

The initial search yielded approximately 150,000 papers. After refining keywords, this number was reduced to 750 relevant studies. Titles and abstracts were screened, resulting in 32 primary studies closely aligned with the research objectives. A snowball method was employed, examining references cited in these selected studies to identify additional relevant literature.

Data Extraction and Synthesis

Data from selected studies were extracted using a structured template, capturing essential information on study characteristics, materials used, production methods, mechanical properties, and environmental impact.

Data Analysis

Data synthesis involved qualitative and quantitative methods. Thematic analysis identified recurring themes and trends across studies, focusing on the effectiveness of different production methods and materials in enhancing carbon absorption. Data visualization techniques illustrated key findings, such as the impact of various supplementary materials on mechanical properties and CO₂ sequestration capabilities.

RESULTS

The results of this systematic review are organized into three main areas: CO₂ reduction methods, mechanical properties of carbon-absorbing concrete, and carbon sequestration potential. Key findings are summarized in tables and visualized in figures to provide a clear comparison of the different materials and methods studied.

CO₂ Reduction Methods

Table 1 summarizes the effectiveness of various methods for reducing the carbon footprint of concrete. Each method is evaluated based on its CO₂ reduction potential, the types of materials used, and additional benefits observed across studies. Notably, replacing a portion of cement with supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs) like fly ash and slag consistently achieved CO₂ reductions ranging from 20% to 60%, while simultaneously improving concrete durability.

Table 1. Comparison of the Various Methods of Reducing Carbon Footprints

Method	Material(s) Used	CO ₂ Reduction (%)	Additional Benefits
Reduction of Cement Content	Fly ash, slag	40-60%	Lower energy consumption, reduced raw material use
Supplementary Cementing Materials (SCMs)	Metakaolin, silica fume, fly ash	20-50%	Enhanced compressive strength, increased durability
Carbon Capture and Injection	Direct CO ₂ curing, carbonation curing	50-75%	Faster curing times, improved concrete stability

Figure 1 illustrates the CO₂ reduction potential of these methods, highlighting that methods incorporating carbon capture and injection can achieve up to 75% CO₂ reduction under optimized conditions.

Figure 1. CO₂ Reduction by Different Methods, Showing that Direct CO₂ Curing and SCMs Like Fly Ash Can Lead to Significant Emission Reductions

Mechanical Properties of SCM-based Carbon-Absorbing Concrete

Table 2 summarizes the effect of carbon foot-prints on mechanical properties of concrete. Figure 2 compares the compressive strength of traditional concrete with SCM-based carbon-absorbing concrete mixes. Studies revealed that SCMs like blast furnace slag and fly ash improve compressive strength by 20-30% compared to standard cement mixes, especially when SCMs are included at optimal replacement ratios (20-30%).

Table 2. The Effect of Carbon Foot-Prints on Mechanical Properties of Concrete

SCM Type	Compressive Strength Improvement (%)	Observed Benefits
Fly Ash	20-25%	Lower heat of hydration, enhanced durability
Metakaolin	15-20%	Improved workability, increased tensile strength
Blast Furnace Slag	25-30%	Greater resistance to chemical attacks, better longevity

Figure 2 shows these results, with SCM-based concretes achieving enhanced compressive strength and durability, which supports their broader adoption in structural applications.

Figure 2. Compressive Strength of SCM-Based Carbon-Absorbing Concrete, Indicating Strength Improvements for Various SCM Types over Conventional Concrete

Carbon Sequestration Potential of Carbon-Absorbing Concrete

Table 3 compares the CO₂ capture capabilities of different sequestration methods, such as carbonation curing and biochar impregnation. Carbonation curing, which involves exposing concrete to CO₂ during curing, achieved CO₂ capture rates of 50-75%, depending on curing conditions. Biochar impregnation, while showing lower sequestration efficiency, improved concrete's overall porosity and increased strength by up to 20%.

Table 3. Comparison of the CO₂ Capture Capabilities of Different Sequestration Methods

Method	Carbon Capture Efficiency (%)	Time Required	Additional Benefits
Carbonation Curing	50-75%	1-2 days	Accelerated curing, improved resistance to corrosion
Biochar Impregnation	15-20%	N/A	Enhanced porosity, increased compressive strength
Graphene Oxide Addition	30-40%	N/A	Improved impermeability, reduced interfacial transition zone width

Figure 3 presents a comparison of lifecycle CO₂ emissions between traditional concrete and carbon-absorbing concrete. The findings suggest that using carbon-absorbing concrete can lead to a reduction of 30-50% in lifecycle emissions, making it a viable sustainable alternative in construction.

Figure 3. Lifecycle CO₂ Emissions of Conventional vs. Carbon-Absorbing Concrete, with Carbon-Absorbing Concrete Options Demonstrating Considerable Lifecycle Emission Reductions

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The results of this systematic review reveal significant potential for carbon-absorbing concrete to address environmental sustainability within the construction sector. The findings demonstrate that various methods and materials can effectively reduce the carbon footprint of concrete while simultaneously enhancing its structural properties. This section discusses these results in light of current knowledge, emphasizing practical implications, limitations, and potential future research directions.

CO₂ Reduction Potential of Different Methods

The study identifies multiple strategies to decrease CO₂ emissions in concrete production, as shown in Figure 1 and Table 1. Among these, carbon capture and injection techniques provide the highest reduction potential, with reductions up to 75% under optimized conditions. This finding underscores the importance of integrating carbon capture technologies, particularly carbonation curing, which not only sequesters CO₂ but also accelerates the curing process, potentially reducing construction time

and costs. These reductions align with recent sustainability goals in the construction industry, emphasizing the role of material innovation in reducing the industry's overall carbon footprint.

In comparison, supplementary cementitious materials (SCMs), such as fly ash and slag, achieved up to 50% CO₂ reduction. This method is advantageous due to its dual benefits: it leverages industrial by-products, thereby reducing waste, and it provides strength and durability enhancements that are comparable to or exceed those of traditional cement. However, SCM availability can vary depending on regional industrial activity, which may limit scalability in areas without consistent access to such by-products.

Enhanced Mechanical Properties with SCMs

The review highlights that SCM-based carbon-absorbing concretes exhibit enhanced compressive strength compared to traditional concrete (Figure 2). This improvement is particularly notable with blast furnace slag, which demonstrated up to a 30% increase in compressive strength. The strength enhancements with SCMs can be attributed to improved microstructure and reduced porosity, which confer greater resistance to external stresses and prolong the lifespan of concrete structures.

Fly ash also showed favorable results, achieving compressive strength improvements of approximately 20-25%. Beyond mechanical strength, fly ash reduces the heat of hydration, which mitigates the risk of thermal cracking—a common issue in mass concrete structures. These findings suggest that SCMs can provide a feasible and economically viable alternative to traditional cement, particularly in projects where durability and longevity are essential. The choice of SCM should consider the specific requirements of the project, including load-bearing capacity, environmental conditions, and long-term maintenance needs.

Carbon Sequestration and Environmental Benefits

The carbon sequestration potential of different methods, as depicted in Table 2 and Figure 3, is a crucial factor in assessing the environmental impact of carbon-absorbing concrete. **Carbonation curing** stands out for its effectiveness in sequestering CO₂, with efficiency rates between 50-75%. This process not only stores CO₂ in a stable form but also enhances the concrete's resistance to degradation mechanisms, such as sulfate attack and chloride ion penetration. By producing a denser and more impermeable microstructure, carbonation curing improves durability, which is essential for structures exposed to aggressive environments.

Other sequestration methods, such as **biochar impregnation**, show moderate carbon capture efficiency (15-20%) but offer additional benefits, including increased porosity and compressive strength. The use of **graphene oxide** similarly improves the impermeability and reduces the interfacial transition zone width, resulting in a denser and more durable concrete mix. These findings point to the potential of combining multiple sequestration techniques to enhance both CO₂ capture and concrete performance. However, further research is needed to optimize the quantities and compositions of these materials to maximize their carbon capture efficiency and minimize costs.

Practical Implications and Future Directions

The adoption of carbon-absorbing concrete presents an exciting opportunity for sustainable construction practices. The findings highlight several practical benefits:

- **Improved structural performance:** SCM-based carbon-absorbing concretes offer superior compressive strength and durability, making them suitable for high-performance applications in infrastructure.
- **Accelerated curing times:** Carbonation curing not only enhances CO₂ sequestration but also reduces construction time, providing both environmental and economic benefits.
- **Sustainability and resource efficiency:** By utilizing industrial by-products, SCM-based concretes reduce waste and support circular economy principles.

However, some challenges remain, including the variability in SCM availability, the cost and scalability of advanced materials like graphene oxide, and the need for long-term durability studies under diverse environmental conditions. Future research should focus on optimizing the material compositions and investigating the feasibility of hybrid methods that combine SCMs with carbon capture technologies to further enhance the CO₂ absorption potential.

Additionally, lifecycle assessments that evaluate the environmental impact of these methods from production through end-of-life would provide valuable insights. Such assessments could help determine the overall sustainability of carbon-absorbing concrete and guide decision-making for large-scale adoption in the construction industry.

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